

SOCIO-ECONOMIC CONDITION AND EDUCATIONAL STATUS OF FEMALE BRICK KILN WORKERS IN KALNA SUBDIVISION AREA OF WEST BENGAL

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Abstract: Fired brick making is highly gender biased work. The women workers, working in brick kilns, are not recognized as workers, they are like invisible or disguised; they don't get even paid adequately for their works and also they have no rights or benefits in these industries. They are quite often sexually abused. The conditions for pregnant women are particularly dreadful, as they don't have access to medical facilities and other necessary amenities. Women are confined by the patriarchal system and are enslaved by the minimum wage. In this paper the researcher showed and discussed the survey based present scenarios of women of brick kiln industry in Kalna subdivision area of West Bengal. The author also discussed their working environment, wages, literacy and reason for migration from native places with their health condition in details.

Keywords: Unorganized sector, Female brick kiln workers, Kalna Subdivision area

1.1 Introduction

The situation of women laborers in India is inferior than most of the developing countries of the world today. Women's poverty in India is directly related to the absence of economic opportunities, autonomy, land ownership and inheritance (Sing, 2003). Labouring women in the informal sector are an important segment of the labour force. They do arduous work as wage earners, piece rate workers, casual labour and paid and unpaid family labour. Their social and economic condition continues to be dismal. Although there is no obvious discrimination against women in the plans and programmes of the government and there are in fact special schemes for the women, in the sphere of implementation, various socio-economic forces operate against them (Majumder, Roychowdhury & Dutta, 2006). However, in spite of all the situation of women, their sharing of economic activity by women is nothing new in our country. From time immemorial they have been working both in the home and outside.

1.2 Background of the Study

Brick industry is located in clusters in different parts of the country where raw materials are available. Brick kilns operate in rural areas throughout the country, for six to eight months a year. There could be as many as 50,000 brick kilns in all, employing about 100 workers each as per the muster rolls. The estimated number of workers would then conservatively be 5 million (since women and children are not included on the muster rolls) (Gupta, 2003).

Brick making is labour intensive work requiring little skill. The semi-skilled workers (*patheras*) involved for the purpose are characterized as contractual family labour working under the bonded labour system. Recruitment is indirect, through a contractor or subcontractor (*jamadar*), who receives commission from the workers. The contractor also channel advances, and is responsible for the labourers' work and debt-servicing. Most of the times he is a co-worker and sometimes he is also a relative of the labourers. The brick kiln workers are offered advances (*peshgi*) through contractors before the work is actually commenced. An informal contract is made between the head of the family (who usually is male) with the brick kiln owner and also is witnessed by the contractor. The head of the family involves most of his family members including males, adolescents, children and women for the preparation of the bricks. Working hours are flexible and families work from dawn to sunset. Brick making is piece rated work, thus the workers are paid on the basis of the number of bricks they or their family prepared. Payment is made on a weekly basis i.e., on every Thursday through the contractor who also deducts his 5% commission. Apart from these deductions the process of advances required by the workers are also made at this time. Actually, Fresh loans are also offered to them during the course of work and so the cycle continues till the workers are completely trapped in it. It is quite difficult for those families to get rid of these debts. Only a few families can manage to get ahead of the game and reduce their debt. This is most likely in a year when a family's children are old enough (12 to 15 years) to work as hard as the adults; the weather is good, and no accidents or illnesses occur. Illness can be a catastrophe. Life events, like weddings, funerals, arrest of a relative, an accident, heavy rains, or anything else that brings extra expenses increase the family debt. Children of the bonded families learn the craft from their parents and continue the profession of their ancestors as their means of livelihood. They actually have to remain in the same profession as they will have to pay off the 'eternal debt' owed by their family due to their parents or parents of their parents. Limited horizontal mobility exists due to migration, however hardly any vertical mobility was seen due to debt and socio-cultural circumstances (SDIBIA, 2003). The labour resides at the kiln in the houses constructed and owned by the owner. These localities lack basic amenities of life such as drinking water, sanitation etc. There hardly exists any school near those vicinities. Workers usually live in remoteness from the local populace with their own culture and customs. It gives rise to crimes like theft and gambling. Their Family size is usually large but the dependency ratio is high. The low wages are not enough to meet the minimum requirements of these large families. As a result the families are caught in the vicious cycle of poverty. They cannot afford even elementary education for their young ones. They lack initiatives and have no potential to migrate to urban areas for higher rewards due to indebtedness and socio-cultural norms. Children and women, being the most vulnerable segment, have to bear the brunt of the burden.

1.3 Women in Brick Kilns

The labour market is not neutral to men and women in brick kiln industries. In this sector it was found that while men do the skilled jobs of brick-laying, women mix mortar and carry head loads of earth and bricks. Women make a significant contribution through family kiln labor across India. They are usually found in the brick fields involved in the making of mud bricks. As advances are binding on the entire family, women being the most vulnerable are the worst affected. They have to work even during pregnancy. Alongside putting in this hard labor they have to do family chores, like preparing food for all the family, collect wood for the fire, bringing water, washing clothes and arranging fodder for the buffaloes or cows, goats etc. They also have to take care of the sick and elderly of the family. Women are even exposed to sexual harassment if their male head of family runs away from the brick kiln. These women hardly get any time for recreation or leisure activities. The life of these women workers is very tough, as they perform dual role relating to production as well as reproduction. They carry the primary responsibility of bearing and rearing their children.

2.1 The Study

The study area was Ambika Kalna in Purba Barddhaman district of West Bengal. Ambika Kalna is situated near the river Bhagirathi & many brick field industries have set up on the bank of it. In the monsoon time when the river Bhagirathi is filled, mud is accumulated in the banks of the river. These accumulated muds are used to produce bricks in these areas. The study was based on primary and secondary sources of data. The primary data was collected through interview with the women workers and the owner of the brick kilns. The secondary data was collected through books, journals, newspapers and from the Report of Brick Association. Percentage analysis and qualitative data analysis were used for interpretation of the data, collected from field survey.

2.2 Research Question

What is the socio-economic condition and educational status of women workers, engaged in brick kilns of Kalna sub-division area?

2.3 Research Objective

The main objective was to examine the socio-economic conditions and educational status of women workers, engaged in brick kilns of Kalna sub-division area.

2.4 Methodology

2.4.1 Design

Descriptive and Survey based research design was used by the researcher.

2.4.2 Tools & Techniques

A self-made interview schedule was prepared and used apart from the voice audio recordings and required photo shots.

2.4.3 Data Collection and Data Analysis

The researcher visited the brick kilns to administer the Interview Schedule in person. She also recorded the whole conversation and has taken required photos there. Then all the data were arranged and analysed in systematic way in the form of table and charts. The researcher also analysed the data qualitatively & descriptively.

3.1 Findings and Interpretations

3.1.1 Findings by Age: For the purpose of the present study, a woman worker who is more than or equal to 15 years of age has been considered. The age composition of the women workers suggests that the majority of the women workers in brick kilns are young. It is evident from chart that more than 86 per cent women working in kilns are below 45 years of age whereas 36 per cent women are between the age of 26 to 35 years and 30 per cent are

between 15 years to 25 years. Thus, it is clear that 66 per cent women workers are younger than even 35 years. As the work in brick kilns require energy & stamina the young women opt for this work as they are able to work more and thus earn more.

3.1.2 Findings by Caste: Caste is always an important determiner of the process of social stratification.

Traditionally, caste and class were associated with the occupations of the people. In the present analysis also, it was observed that the maximum workers in the brick kiln industry comes from the lower castes of the society. Chart reveals that almost all (99 per cent) the women workers were from the castes other than the higher castes. There was only one worker out of the total sample who was from the higher castes, whereas all

other workers were either from the backward castes or the scheduled castes. The scheduled castes consisted mainly of the *Chamars*, *Valmikis* and the *Dhanaks* whereas the *Kumhaars* is the main backward caste working in large numbers in the brick kilns of this division. The analysis further reveals that there were as large as 82 per cent women workers of scheduled castes, 13 per cent of backward castes and just 1 per cent of the higher castes. Thus, we see that the women from scheduled castes and the backwards castes form the major chunk of the labour force in the brick kiln industry.

3.1.3 Findings of Educational Qualification:

An analysis of the level of education of the respondents indicates that most (91 per cent) of the women workers in the brick kilns were illiterate. There were just a small proportion of 9 per cent women workers who had acquired some formal school education. 6 per cent women stated to have studied up to IVth standard while, 2 per cent said to have passed Xth class. A negligibly small proportion of just 1 per cent had passed XIIth class. There was not even a single woman in this sample who had passed graduation or post graduation. The trend was more or less the same across all the five districts of this division. Some minor differences observed was only coincidental and no specific reason can be prescribed to these differences.

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3.1.4 Findings about Place of Living:

The living quarters of the workers in brick kilns were observed to be quite inadequate and unsatisfactory. These workers have not been provided with proper facilities of drinking water, sanitation and education. The living arrangements for these workers can be classified of four types, i.e., *pakka* quarters, *kachcha* quarters, huts and their own houses in nearby villages. The chart reveals that nearly 26 per cent live in *kachcha* quarters, 61 per cent live in *pakka* quarters. 11 per cent of them live in huts. There were just about 2 per cent workers who used to go to their villages in the evenings. It was also observed that the workers in brick kilns preferred to live with their fellow workers only i.e. the workers of their own native state.

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3.1.5 Findings of Types of Workers:

In the survey, it was found that there were many types of labourers in brickfield industry. Those who are doing the work for many consecutive years they can be called skilled workers, those who are doing the work for some years can be called Semi-skilled workers and those who just joined there can be called unskilled workers. Here it was found that in brick kiln 42 per cent of the workers are skilled workers, 34 per cent workers are semi-skilled workers and rest 24 per cent workers of them are unskilled workers. And here it was also found that there were almost no skilled women workers in those brick fields. All the women are doing only the work as semi-skilled or unskilled laborers.

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4.1 Conclusion

The present enquiry proposes the concerned state government for a Brick Kiln Manual which would act as a comprehensive legislation to regulate the working and living conditions of the workers of brick kiln industry. Apart from it, recruitment procedures of the workers in this industry must be streamlined. Either the workers be regularized on the pattern of government cooperative sugar mills or they may be issued service cards. Provisions must be made at the district level to register the intermediaries actively involved in procuring the workers for the owners of the brick kilns. They must be provided licenses as is given in Inter State Migrants Workers Act 1979 and the Contract Labour Act 1970. Government should constitute a tripartite committee every year at the state level to decide about the rates of wages, the bonus and the incentives for these workers. Efforts should also be made by the enforcement machinery to effectively implement the recommendations of this committee. Role of trade unions and NGOs in this connection is recommended. Voluntary organizations/social activists and trade unions can work towards making improvements in their health status, educational attainments and general welfare. Last but not the least, the government should give a considerable attention to the brick kiln industry and the problems of its workers and employers as the industry provides a pivotal support to all developmental activities relating to buildings and constructions, in the country.

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